

E-LEARNING AND A THREAT OF LEARNING LOSS

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Abstract :

Online learning supplements traditional learning and helps in regaining learning loss. Learners learn online and gain knowledge through technology. But the paradox is that all-time online learning itself is resulting in learning loss as it is distracting learners, creating technological issues, chances of the untaught syllabus, negativity in learning, absence of social interaction, and learning environment. It was assumed that online learning may bring revolution in medication of behavior of the learners. But today, it is being realized that the degrees from online learning are being unvalued and it is a threat not only to learning but also in chasing a good career. The results show handsome scores but the fundamental knowledge and practicability have been in question. The findings show that even the learners are not comfortable with online learning and understand the threat of learning loss.

Key words: *online/virtual learning, learners, learning loss*

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Introduction :

Background of the Study :

Learning is nothing but a modification of behavior. Learners are not taught to understand but to modify their behavior during and after the post-learning process. The traditional teaching-learning method is mainly associated with classroom teaching, where the teachers and students interact, learners find friends, and become social by interacting with them. For years, this method of education is being used in India. But since the emergence of the Covid-19, the face of the entire education system has got changed. Now the teaching and learning take place online and both teachers and learners have no option but to adopt this kind of platform to impart and gain knowledge. Online learning is a learning that is imparted by using technology and is highly technical.

Problem Statement :

It is believed that online learning can remove learning loss by supplementing missed courses in classroom teaching. But there is a paradox to it. Rather online learning now, is responsible for learning loss as learners are stressed, distracted and take online learning easy. It was believed that online learning would be the solution to gain additional

knowledge, but now, when the entire learning process became online, it is observed that it has become the main cause of ‘learning losses among the learners. There is no surety and guarantee of learning outcomes in virtual learning. And the threat is that the generation learning under this method may have degrees with handsome marks but without knowledge with neutral behavior. Therefore, this paper is being presented to highlight the perception towards, problems, effects of online learning, and reality of learning loss.

Significance of the Study :

Undoubtedly online learning helped learners to continue their learning during the pandemic situation. Teachers and learners managed to be a part of the teaching and learning process. But replacing the traditional classroom with this method, changing the entire learning process, may make learners passive, may discourage learners who like face-to-face teaching, may harm students who do not have the technical facility and are not used to using computers and mobiles. etc. It is also noted sure if the learners would be self-motivated in eLearning and understand its benefits. Therefore, this study is important as it would highlight what learners think about all the time eLearning.

Objectives of the Study :

1. To discuss eLearning and its relevance in the present time.
2. To find out the perception of the learners toward eLearning gender-wise.
3. To explore problems and effects of eLearning in the light of learning loss.

Literature Review :

Balarabe, Y. (2006) studied effects of the blended e-learning on practical subjects like maths and computer learning. The learning attitude was the main focus of this study. **Bekele, T.A., & Menchaca, M.P. (2009)**. Carried a study in Ethiopia on critical thinking and skills of problem-solving in blended learning among students. **Benson, D.S. (2005)** studied the nature of hybrid and learning methods. In the classroom and online their characteristics. **Buket, A., & Meryem, Y.S. (2006)**. Found out students’ views on blended learning and its impact in Turkey. **Chen, C.C., & Jones, K.T. (2007)**. compared traditional classroom learning and traditional learning and also assessed the effectiveness and perception among MBA students. **Dean, P., Stahl, M., Sylwester, D., & Pear, J. (2001)** studied the effectiveness of combined delivery modalities for online and distance learning and its impact on learning. **Ferdinand, P. (2004)**. Focused on self-directed learning and eLearning and its experiments. they gave importance to blending learning promoted among young minds in natural sciences in Italy. **Ferreira, L.B.M. (2004)**. carried a study on the learning science of fifth-grade learners and its philosophy. **Harding, A., Kaczynski, D., & Wood, L. (2005)**. Evaluated blended learning and analyzed data to come out with its results in Sydney. **Herman, T., & Banister, S. (2007)**. Carried a study on face-to-face versus online learning and mentioned cost and learning outcomes. **Meenakshi Thanji, Dr.S. Vasantha, (2016)** stated the drivers and barriers in online learning and E-commerce offering for education in India.

Research Methodology :

- Primary Data is collected from 650 learners from the Junior, degree, and PG sections to understand learning loss in online learning from their end. The data is collected by distribution questionnaires framed by using Closed-ended questions and questions based on the Likert scale.
- Secondary data is derived from already published papers, reference books, theses, and reports.
- The sampling method used to collect data non-probability convenience sampling to draw general views. The total sample size was 650. This study is descriptive and explorative. A T-test is used to find out Gender wise perception related to online learning dimensions.

Analysis of the Data :
a. Reliability Test :

A Cronbach alpha coefficient was calculated for the E-Learning Benefits scale, E-Learning Problems, Effects of E-Learning, and Opinion on E-Learning. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was evaluated using the guidelines suggested by George and Mallery (2018) where $> .9$ excellent, $> .8$ good, $> .7$ acceptable, $> .6$ questionable, $> .5$ poor, and $< .5$ unacceptable.

Reliability Table for E-Learning Benefits

Scale	No. of Items	α	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
E-Learning Benefits	7	.76	.73	.78
E-Learning Problems	9	.86	.85	.88
Effects of E-Learning	11	.88	.87	.89
Opinion on E-Learning	5	.70	.67	.74

Note. The lower and upper bounds of Cronbach's α were calculated using a 95.00% confidence interval.

b. Data Related to eLearning :

Diagram 1 : Gender

out of 650 learners, 45 percent are girls and 55 percent are boys who responded to the questionnaire. To avail the proper data, both gender are considered in data collection.

Diagram 2 : Class

out of 650 learners, 58 percent were from the junior section, 34 percent from the degree section, and 8 percent from the post-graduation section. The data was only collected from learners from the commerce and management stream.

Diagram 3: Liking eLearning?

out of 650 learners, 55.7 percent learners expressed their view that they like online learning and enjoy it. Whereas 28.5 percent expressed their disliking towards online learning. 15.8 percent were not sure if they like online learning or not. They were more unsure about it.

Diagram 4 : Loss of real learning

Out of 650 learners, nearly 46.9 percent feel that there is a loss of learning in eLearning due to many factors such as personal, technical, curriculum, evaluation, etc. 28.6 percent of learners do not feel so. Whereas 24.5 percent of learners were unable to understand its advantages and disadvantages. They were unsure of learning loss.

Diagram 5: Perception towards online Learning

Out of 650 learners, 20.3 percent feel that learning online is an excellent experience. 9.2 percent feel that it is a very good experience. 11.5 percent expressed that the experience is so-so and not so comfortable. Whereas 35.4 percent mentioned that it is very bad and 23.5 expressed it as worst and do not support it at all.

Diagram 6 : Result of Online learning

Out of 650 learners,

- 48.6 percent of learners mentioned strongly disagree, 9.1 percent mentioned disagree, with the statement 'online learning is flexible.' Therefore, it can be stated that an average number of learners do feel it is flexible and support it.
- 41.8 percent of learners mentioned strongly disagree, 16.9 percent mentioned disagree, with the statement 'online learning is very effective.' Therefore, it can be stated that more than an average number of learners find online learning ineffective whereas others find it effective.
- 42 percent of learners mentioned strongly disagree, 21.2 percent mentioned disagreeing, 22.3 percent mentioned neither agree nor disagree, 4.5 percent mentioned agree and 10 percent strongly agree with the statement 'online learning is good for understanding'. It means almost 63.2 percent of learners do not find it useful as a good understanding, 22.3 shared no feelings.
- 58.6 percent expressed that it should not be continued whereas others wanted it to be continued. Nearly 60.7 percent mentioned that online learning does not ensure good knowledge and is futile. Almost 75.6 percent mentioned that online learning results in learning loss and knowledge are being not gained. 64.3 percent of learners believed that online learning does not connect teaches and learners being virtual and offline classrooms.

Diagram 7 : Problems in online learning.

Regarding problems in online learning,

- 70.1 percent believed that there is a problem in conceptual understanding.73.7 percent believed that there is a problem in practical learning and experience
- 67.8 percent expressed that it is not good for practical subjects like maths and accountancy as the hand-on practice is not there and mere watching slides do not fulfill their curiosity of understanding.68.8 percent expressed that there is partial learning and threat in learning curriculum in full.
- 61.7 percent of learners mentioned that learners avoid learning and there is an easy way to get escaped from learning. There is indiscipline in learning.54.3 percent found online learning boring and unengaging. Nealy 72 percent believed that there is a technical problem many a time and it affects smooth learning. 70.9 percent believed that there is only listening and very little chance is provided for interaction. Whereas 60.6 percent believed that for theoretical subjects, it is quite boring

Diagram 8 : Effects of Online Learning

Out of 650 learners,

72.8 percent expressed that online learning results in less and partial knowledge, 70.9 percent believed there is no real and fruitful learning, 73.7 percent doubts getting employed on the degrees received through online learning. 71.3 percent agreed that it is only giving degrees with no fruitful learning. 70.5 percent of learners believed that they would always be tagged and teased for their degrees. 70.2 percent believed that they only would get high marks without a high level of knowledge. 71.7 believed that they do not have good social interaction and virtually they cannot be so connected with classmates as well as with the teachers. Almost 74.7 percent of learners believed that there is a threat in creating a sound educational and learning base through online learning unless the learner is sincere and takes learning on priority. And 69.2 percent believe that online learning is a threat to the career.

Diagram 9 : Overall Experience with Online Learning

out of 650 learners, only 14.2 percent believe that the Learning experience is excellent, 13.8 percent believe that it is very good. 30.3 percent believe that it is very bad, 17.7 percent mentioned it as so-so and 24.2 percent straightway mentioned that it is worst. Therefore, the majority are not happy with online learning.

Hypothesis Testing :

Sr.no	Hypothesis	Result of Two-tailed T-test
1.	not a statistically significant difference in the E-Learning Benefits by the categories of the Gender.	The result of the two-tailed independent samples <i>t</i> -test was significantly based on an alpha value of .05, $t(648) = -2.87, p = .004$, indicating the null hypothesis can be rejected. This finding suggests the mean of E-Learning Benefits was significantly different between the Female and Male categories of Gender.
2.	not a statistically significant difference in the E-Learning Problems by the categories of the Gender.	The result of the two-tailed independent samples <i>t</i> -test was not significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(433.62) = 0.27, p = .785$, indicating the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This finding suggests the mean of E-Learning Problems was not significantly different between the Female and Male categories of Gender.

3	not a statistically significant difference in the Effects of E-Learning by the categories of Gender.	The result of the two-tailed independent samples <i>t</i> -test was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(449.93) = 2.03, p = .043$, indicating the null hypothesis can be rejected. This finding suggests the mean of Effects of E-Learning was significantly different between the Female and Male categories of Gender
4.	not a statistically significant difference in the Opinion on E-Learning by the categories of Gender.	The result of the two-tailed independent samples <i>t</i> -test was not significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(648) = -1.90, p = .058$, indicating the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This finding suggests the mean of Opinion on E-Learning was not significantly different between the Female and Male categories of Gender

Concussion :

In this study, it is observed that although learners enjoyed online learning in the short run as they are not pressed with compulsory classroom learning, assignments, and attendance. But they too realize the threat of eLearning in the long run. More than seventy percent of learners are not in favour of all-time online learning. Rather they do want it as blending learning to recover the learning loss along with classroom learning. The major findings show that eLearning is not being preferred by good learners and those who keep social intelligence.

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